

BPI Ri-4 is resistant to BPH biotype 1, appears to have field resistance to biotype 2, and is moderately resistant to stem borers. Current Masagana 99 crop protection recommendations do not include insecticide control for either "early" or "late" stem borers. BPH, a minor problem in the Philippines in 1978, was serious in 1977.

The average yields from 43 irrigated rice farms in 20 provinces are shown in the table.

Soil-incorporated granular carbofuran at as little as 0.5 kg a.i./ha returned high

Average yields from 43 irrigated farmers' fields in 20 provinces, Philippines, 1978 wet season.

Insecticide rate ^a (kg a.i./ha)	Yield (t/ha)	Yield increase (t/ha)	Value of increase at US\$0.15/kg	Cost of US\$ granular carbofuran	Increase in profit (US\$/ha)
0	4.0	—	—	—	—
0.5	4.7	0.7	105	15	90
0.75	5.0	1.0	150	22	128
1.00	5.1	1.1	165	30	135

^a Other Masagana 99 insect control recommendations: 5 kg ZnSO₄/ha, MTMC spray at 0.75 kg a.i./ha applied to all treatments 50 days after transplanting.

profits from the control of early season insect pests, primarily the whorl maggot and stem borers, on farms.

The Philippines may recommend soil

incorporation of granular carbofuran for the Masagana 99 national rice production program for the 1979 wet season (beginning in May). ■

Evaluation of systemic effect of insecticides against brown planthopper

P. R. M. Rao and P. S. Prakasa Rao, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, Orissa, India

Of about 100 species of insect pests that attack rice in India, the brown planthopper (BPH) is the major one in many states. BPH epidemics have become frequent since about 1970. Chemical control measures are not satisfactory because the nymphs and adults remain at the base of the rice plant and the thick plant canopy forms an air cover, preventing the insecticidal spray from reaching them. To overcome this limitation studies were conducted to identify insecticides capable of killing the insect even if they are superficially applied on the crop foliage.

Aqueous solutions of 14 commercial insecticide preparations were applied as

0.05% sprays on the upper foliage of 1-month-old potted plants of TN1. The plants' basal 15-cm portions were covered with masks. The insecticides were sprayed with a fine atomizer until the runoff stage. The sprayed plants were kept in open air for 24 hours. Then the treated foliage was cut off and the plants were enclosed in cages. Ten healthy BPH adults were confined on each plant. Mortality was recorded at 12 and 24 hours after the insects' exposure to the treated plants. The experiment was replicated three times.

Chlorpyrifos had the highest systemic effect, followed by carbofuran, quinalphos, methamidophos, dicotophos, and phosphamidon (see table). The insecticides would be promising where the dense rice canopy prevents superficial insecticidal sprays from reaching the basal plant parts, where nymphs and adults remain. ■

Evaluation of systemic effect of some candidate insecticides applied as 0.05% foliar sprays against brown planthopper adults.^a 11-13 April 1977, Central Rice Research Institute, India.

Insecticide	Corrected mortality ^b (%)	
	12 hours	24 hours
Chlorpyrifos	100	100
Phosphamidon	33	63
Carbofuran	77	77
Carbaryl	40	40
Dicotophos	50	63
Monocrotophos	33	53
Quinalphos	47	67
Dimethoate	23	43
Methamidophos	50	67
SAN 197	0	30
Vamidothion	0	0
Dichlorvos	0	0
Control	0	0

^aMax temp = 34.4°C, min temp = 22.2°C, mean max temp = 33.7°C, mean min temp = 24.3°C, mean relative humidity = 74%.

^b Treated foliage portion cut off 24 hours after insects were exposed to treatment.

Emergence of rice leaf butterfly as a rice pest in Manipur, India

S. Amu Singh, Plant Protection Section, Directorate of Agriculture, Imphal, Manipur, India (present address: Lake Hall 12, Kalyani, Nadia, West Bengal 741235, India)

Until 1973, the rice leaf butterfly *Melanitis leda ismene* Cramer was unknown to farmers of Manipur state. The first extensive infestation of the insect in the state was in 1973 kharif in Imphal, the central district, on a few new high-yielding and two local varieties (see table). The pest was noticed in the field in early August at the maximum tillering

stage of the main second crop and infestation continued until late November when the crop was almost mature. Horned caterpillars of the butterfly fed on the

tender foliage in late morning and early evening, and sometimes caused severe defoliation. Fields planted to second crops with ensured water supply were

Infestation of rice leaf butterfly on rice. Centra district, Imphal, Manipur, India

Variety	Location	Area infested ^a (ha)	Time	Plant parts infested
IR8	Changangei	4.05	Aug	Leaves
IR24	Kakching, Yurembam, Tabungkhok	81.00	Jul-Aug	Leaves
Ratna	Kakching	16.20	Jul-Aug	Leaves
Jaya	Changangei, Thoubal	4.05	Aug	Leaves
Moirangphou (local variety)	Kakching	40.50	Aug	Leaves, stem
Phourel (local variety)	Thoubal	6.07	Aug	Leaves, stem

^aConverted from acres.

attacked more heavily than first-crop fields. Rice fields under shifting cultivation on hill slopes were not infested.

A study was made in 1973 kharif to determine the extent of infestation and the "hot spots" in Imphal, where most rice cultivation is confined.

The pest is well established in the major rice belt of Manipur, extending south to the Bishenpur block and north to Kangpokpi. Observations during the past 4 to 5 years confirm that the pest is building up in the state, necessitating regular chemical control as that for yellow stem borer and gall midge.

Further buildup of the pest cannot be ruled out, considering the changed agricultural strategy in Manipur brought about by the introduction of more high-yielding varieties, the extension of areas under such varieties, heavier fertilizer applications, and increased cropping intensity. Along with the rice caseworm *Nymphula depunctalis*, leaf butterfly is fast emerging as a pest at early growth stages of the second paddy crop — the bulk of rice production in the state. ■

Chemical control of the brown planthopper

Covinda Natar, R & D Officer, Mysore Agro Chemical Company, Box 908, Mangalore 5, India

A study to determine suitable pesticides for control of the brown planthopper (BPH) was conducted in our field in kharif 1978.

The trial was laid out in a randomized block design, replicated four times. The insecticides fenitrothion, monocrotophos, ethion, and quinalphos at 0.05%

Brown planthopper incidence and rice yields on plots treated with various chemicals. Mangalore, India.

Treatment ^a	BPH (mean no./ 5 hills)	Mean yield (kg/plot)
Fenitrothion	27.2	2.0
Monocrotophos	15.2	2.3
Ethion	8.0	3.0
Quinalphos	35.2	1.8
Control	67.5	0.9
CD at 0.5%	12.57	0.22

^aAll treatments applied at 0.05%.

concentration were compared with an untreated control. They were sprayed at crop growth stages from the nursery to the hard dough stage. The BPH on five randomly selected hills per replication were counted before and periodically after each spraying.

All the insecticidal sprays significantly reduced BPH infestation and increased yields over that of the control (see table). Treatments with ethion were most effective, followed by those with monocrotophos and fenitrothion. ■

Hopperburn by the orange-headed leafhopper in Bangladesh

Shamsul Alam and M. S. Alam, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Joydebpur, Dacca, Bangladesh

In Bangladesh, hopperburn caused by the brown planthopper, whitebacked planthopper, and green leafhopper was previously reported. This is the first report on hopperburn caused by the orange-headed leafhopper (OHLH) *Thaia oryzivora* Ghauri.

Ghauri (1962) described the new genus *Thaia* and the new species *Thaia oryzivora* on paddy in Thailand. Smaller than *Nephotettix* spp., OHLH can be easily identified by its orange-colored head and subhyaline fore wings. This leafhopper was first recorded in Bangladesh — on wheat in 1964 and on rice in 1968 — by H. Z. Alam. Ahmed and Samad (1972) regarded the insect as a pest of economic importance in Bangladesh. It usually feeds on the undersurface of leaves, causing necrotic lesions around feeding sites. The badly affected leaves show white scars or irregular lines on the upper surfaces. Adults and nymphs produce similar damage. Alam and Alam (1977) reported that the insect breeds actively in October and November and again in February and March, producing high populations during those periods.

Hopperburn occurred the last week of March in areas with controlled irrigation in the Dacca area. There was standing water in the fields and rice growth was luxuriant. Hopperburn occurred from flowering to the hard dough stage in IR8, especially that planted in November or

early December. It did not occur on BR3, BR6, and Pajam II. Although OHLH caused negligible hopperburn, it is a potential pest of rice in Bangladesh. ■

Chironomid fauna of Korea and their role in the rice agroecosystem

K. Yasumatsu, Entomology and Zoology Division, Department of Agriculture, Bangkok, Bangkok 9, Thailand; H. Hashimoto, Biology Department, Faculty of Education, Shizuoka University, Shizuoka, Japan; and Y. D. Chang, Department of Entomology, Institute of Agricultural Sciences, Office of Rural Development, Suweon, Korea

Chironomids are the most numerous insects in the rice paddy ecosystem in Korea. However, the significance of chironomid fauna in the ecosystem is not known.

In the summer 1975, Yasumatsu and Chang collected chironomids in the rice paddies of Suweon, Korea. Hashimoto identified the specimens as follows:

1. *Smittia* sp.
2. *Mesosmittia* (?) sp.
3. *Chironomus nipponensis* Tokunaga
4. *Chironomus plumosus* Linnaeus
5. *Syncricotopus rufiventris* (Meigen)
6. *Cricotopus trifasciatus* Panzer
7. *Harnischia* sp.
8. *Orthocladus suspensus* Tokunaga
9. *Eukiefeeriella* sp.

The only chironomid species previously reported from Korea is *Chironomus oryzae* Matzumura. But it was not identified by a specialist. We believe that the species identified as *Chironomus oryzae* is *C. plumosus*. More material is still under taxonomic study by Hashimoto, and more species will later be added to the list.

Most species of chironomids breed in dead organic matter and the adults emerge in large numbers. Predators, such as spiders and damselflies, feed on them and also on pests that breed on the rice plant (see figure).

Chironomids are significant to the agrosystem. Throughout the vast rice areas of Asia they serve as an alternative food of predators and thus help conserve predators when rice pests are scarce. Chironomids are often more abundant and easily captured than rice pests.